

The Alpha- Process Mining Maturity Model (α -HP3M)

Focus Area	Capability	Level	Sub Dimension
Technology	Assess the information capability and analytic process in process mining	4 levels	Information Capability Analytic Process
Data	Assess the state and availability of data for process mining as an analytic capability as well as the associated data security and data quality policies and standards	5 levels	Data Availability Data Security Data Quality
Pipeline	Assess the state of PM workflow automated (from data gathering to their analysis and diffusion of the results) and how the data are gathered to be integrated and transformed into an event log that can be used for the workflow.	5 levels	Tooling Integration with Data Source Integration with Operational Application
Strategic Alignment	Assess the strategy that examines the plan of action and roadmap support of process mining as an analytic capability	5 levels	Strategy Budgeting Business Contribution
Governance	Assess how an organization sets the formal rules and structures, including their documentation, regarding process mining as an analytical capability	5 levels	Communication Quality Metric Documentation System and Compliance Check
Culture	Assess the collective values shaping the attitude and behavior when human resources use process mining as analytical capability in their job	5 levels	Use Case Availability Management Involvement Adaptability Consistency
People	Assess how the human resources are managed in the organization to support process mining as an analytic capability	5 levels	Skill Responsibility

Technology Dimension

Assess the information capability and analytic process in process mining

Sub Dimension	PM Initiated	Diagnostic and Descriptive	Predictive	Prescriptive
Information Capability	Get process map visualizations, deliver simple insight about process in the organizations	<p>Getting insight into the event logs history, root cause analysis might be helpful to understand the reason and suggest for some core business process</p> <p>Analysis result is linked to value stream SLAs/KPI's using dashboard</p>	<p>Process mining result have predictive capability, using it for alerts and forecasting</p> <p>The dashboard gives some value with SLA/KPI's that align with business strategy</p>	The recommendation gives information about what, when, and why an event or trend might happen and tells what actions have the highest potential for the best outcome. It allows the decision to fix problems, improve performance, or gives some valuable opportunities
Analytic Process	Doing process discovery and conformance checking In some area of organizations	Simple analytic with diagnostic and descriptive capability, AI might be detected	Doing prediction using AI to the business use case to give some recommendation and supports daily process management across different department	Learn from historical, prediction and implementation result to triggers situationally aware automations or giving valuable actions needed for the ongoing system

Data Dimension

Assess the state and availability of data for process mining as an analytic capability as well as the associated data security and data quality policies and standards

Sub Dimension	Initial	Managed	Defined	Quantitatively Managed	Optimized
Data Availability	Recognize relevant data for process mining	Pay attention to data acquisition standards for process mining	Propose data acquisition standards for the core business units	Establish data acquisition standard across multiple departments	optimize smart data acquisition across all industrial processes within departments of the enterprises
Data Security	Have data security plan for IT environment	Pay general attention to data security management for IT environment	Make both technical and non-technical to deal with data security management for core business units	Implement data security management tools and plan across different departments and pay particular attention to IoT based cyber security	Optimize data security management and practices across targeted industrial processes of the firm to eliminate any potential cyber risks in an SM environment
Data Quality	Identify the format of input and data output for each system	One-sided and non-historical sample size Difficult to transfer and unstructured data	Capture of essential features, but small sample, Limited transferable and semi-structured formats	Coverage relevant features, large sample with unequally distributed classes, directly transferable and mixed scale formats	Capture all relevant features, large sample, overlapping and standardized format, structured and metric-scale format
	Identify the need of data quality for business process	Pay attention to dealing with data quality problems for process mining	Make plans to deal with data quality problems for core business process	Standardize data cleansing and consolidation across the organization / multiple departments	optimize data quality across targeted industrial processes within departments of the enterprises

Pipeline Dimension

Assess the state of PM workflow automated (from data gathering to their analysis and diffusion of the results) and how the data are gathered to be integrated and transformed into an event log that can be used for the workflow.

Sub Dimension	Initial	Managed	Defined	Quantitatively Managed	Optimized
Tooling	Use commercial tool or develop the apps to do limited capabilities of process mining function	Use commercial tool or develop the apps with advanced capabilities, need to pay or need to define specific business use case	Use commercial tool or develop apps and using data that connected with ongoing process also generate the dashboard for visualization	Use commercial tool or develop apps, use the data from ongoing system, visualize it and give prediction or alert to fulfill certain KPI	Develop integrated platform with ongoing system (full commercial tools or customize with own code), make prediction and prescriptive alert also authorize automated action needed
Integration with Data Source	Data sources need to be downloaded and adjusted to the process mining needs	Data sources was standardized to fulfill process mining needs, having initial plan for automated data sources integration with process mining module	Get the integration with the data source and create ongoing dashboard	Ongoing dashboard can show the prediction and make recommendation	Get the most up to date of existing data for latest predictive or prescriptive technique, data history 'learning' may support actionable decision
Integration with Operational Applications	Independent PM process, not connected with operational application	Define which operational application that can relate to process mining plan, connect the data needed with other department/ business functional	Use PM experiments to build support for breaking down data silos and consolidating data for core business case	Ongoing dashboards connect with operational application and make suggestion for ongoing system	The process mining function connect all needed operational application throughout organization

Strategic Alignment Dimension

Assess the strategy that examines the plan of action and roadmap support of process mining as an analytic capability

Sub Dimension	Initial	Managed	Defined	Quantitatively Managed	Optimized
Strategy	Align business and technical leaders on the need for Process Mining Awareness	Use PM Proofs of Concept (POCs) to align leadership on PM investment	Define PM strategy and communicate to the organization, Gain budget and sponsorship for PM Project	Align PM strategy with other organizational roadmaps	Sustain momentum to keep innovating and transforming
Budgeting	No PM Strategy, No PM Budgets	Short Term Strategy, but no dedicated PM budgets yet,	Medium Term PM Strategy and Dedicated Pm Budgets	Dedicated PM Budgets	Long Term PM Strategy Dedicated PM Budgets
Business Contribution	No Measure for Business Contribution	There will be measurement in Business contribution	Define the number for business Contribution	Giving a monitoring status for business contribution	Using business contribution for PM in the Quality Management System as KPI

Governance Dimension

Assess how an organization sets the formal rules and structures, including their documentation, regarding process mining as an analytical capability

Sub Dimension	Initial	Managed	Defined	Quantitatively Managed	Optimized
Communication	Understand the consequence and Challenge with PM Plan	Involve different stakeholders to gain a complete view of challenges and opportunities	Synthesize PM Plan to Practice and Guidance	Build organizational structures to manage the strength and scalability of PM	Engage with the PM Community to compare achievement
Quality Metric	Identify PM Implementation in the roadmap	Translate principles into concrete responsibilities, processes, and metrics	Standardize governance practices with supporting technology such as reporting tools	Standardize governance practices with Corrective Action	Standardized governance practice with Preventive Plan
Documentation System and Compliance Check	No Operating Procedure Established	SOP Established but Not Fully Implemented	SOP Implemented and Monitoring Documented	SOP Implemented, Monitoring Documented and KPI Recorded	Use the Feedback from Monitoring and KPI for Continuous Improvement

Culture Dimension

Assess the collective values shaping the attitude and behavior when human resources use process mining as analytical capability in their job

Sub Dimension	Initial	Managed	Defined	Quantitatively Managed	Optimized
Use Case Availability	See the Business Case Urgency but not managed	See the Business Case Urgency, make pilot project use case, define the method to apply PM	Connect with Other Department to Develop Solution, Use Case in Specific Business Case	Make Standardized Procedure and Integrated in the System	Create Quality Management Cycle for All Process (PDCA)
Management involvement	Rely on individual for change and problems	Have initiatives per department but lack of synergy	Have synergy and communication with another department	Have business and IT align for integration	Executive level sponsorship and integration in corporate strategy
Adaptability	React on customer problem based on the case	Start to have customer focus plan, accept customer sound	Define the standard, procedure based on customer need	Have measurement for customer need and satisfaction to the business process	Customer focus strategy, customer insight data as input and optimize it based on measurement result
Consistency	No consistency among the process business management	Recognize the business process and change management	Define the procedure for change management	Have the mechanism to measure and review the change management	Have optimized step to do continuous improvement in agreement for change management

People Dimension

Assess how the human resources are managed in the organization to support process mining as an analytic capability

Sub Dimension	Initial	Managed	Defined	Quantitatively Managed	Optimized
Skill	Basic Understanding of Process Mining Workflow Available, trial on new knowledge	Ability to perform of Process Mining Workflow Available	Ability to performs data analysis and decision making, understand the use of AI	Ability to perform complex analysis in Process Mining, may use AI in practice	Trained in Process Mining integrate with AI and empower other people
Responsibility	Getting help from Process Mining specialist to identify and solve knowledge gap	Form Ad Hoc team to identify the need of process mining implementation	Connect PM team with cross functional business process	Identify PM team with structure and responsibilities	Empower talent strategy for new skills and roles required for process mining